

DMP for Digital Tools in Entrepreneurship Education: the Impact on Entrepreneurial Intention and Attraction of Development Funding (DEFINT)

Version 1

Description

Project funded by:

- EU Recovery Fund Project: No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007
- Internal Grant: LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0068

The project investigates the role of digital tools in entrepreneurship education (EE) and their impact on fostering entrepreneurial intention (EI) and readiness to attract development funding. Special attention is given to gender differences, particularly improving women's access to resources, and the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) within these tools.

Key objectives include:

- Mapping existing digital tools in EE and their functionalities, with a focus on AI integration.
- Assessing the influence of digital tools on EI and development funding capabilities through workshops, experiments, and statistical analysis.
- Evaluating gender-based differences in outcomes and proposing improvements to enhance inclusivity and effectiveness of digital tools.

The study's outputs include recommendations for designing EE tools that cater to diverse user groups, including higher education institutions, policymakers, development finance institutions, and non-governmental organizations.

Project manager: Ph.D. Kristaps Lešinskis, 1 September 2024 – 28 February 2026, 199 996 EUR

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Internal and External
Consolidation of the University
of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia, BA School of Business and Finance

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP for Digital Tools in Entrepreneurship Education: the Impact on Entrepreneurial Intention and Attraction of Development Funding (DEFINT)

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Organizations:

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Contact: Lešinkis Kristaps (Kristaps.Lesinskis@ba.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project:

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Dataset on the Impact of Digital Tools on Entrepreneurial Intention and Readiness to Attract Development Finance

This dataset contains survey responses collected during controlled experiments comparing traditional and digital tool-enhanced approaches in entrepreneurship education. The data focuses on pre- and post-session survey results, specifically evaluating the potential of digital tools to positively influence entrepreneurial intention and improve participants' readiness to attract development finance.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose:

The purpose of data collection is to evaluate the impact of digital tools on entrepreneurial education by comparing learning outcomes and entrepreneurial intention in groups exposed to traditional versus digital tool-enhanced teaching methods.

Origin:

The data will be generated through pre- and post-session surveys conducted via online tools like Google Forms or Microsoft Forms. These surveys will capture participant responses during controlled experiments, forming the basis for testing research hypotheses aligned with the project objectives.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- ODS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, the possibility of re-using existing data was considered. However, while existing datasets may inform related research questions or methodologies, they do not directly address the specific objectives of this study. Therefore, new data collection is required to evaluate the impact of digital tools on learning outcomes and entrepreneurial intention in the context of this project.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The collected dataset will be useful to stakeholders involved in entrepreneurship education and policy-making, including higher education institutions, development finance institutions, governmental organizations, and non-governmental organizations. Additionally, the data may be valuable for researchers investigating the impact of digital tools on entrepreneurial intention and gender differences in entrepreneurial readiness.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

No, we do not plan to provide additional metadata for the dataset. The dataset's structure and field names will be sufficiently clear for users to understand and utilize it without requiring additional documentation.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Digital Tools, Entrepreneurial Intention, Gender Differences, Development Finance

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

Comment:

No, there will be no embargo period applied. The data will be openly accessible immediately after publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

GitHub

GitHub is a widely recognized platform among the project team for data storage, collaboration, and version control, ensuring data transparency and accessibility. The project team is already familiar with GitHub, making it an ideal choice for publicly sharing data in alignment with open science principles.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

To access the data, software tools such as Excel or any spreadsheet software, R, and JASP are needed. These tools will allow users to process, analyze, and visualize the dataset effectively. Additionally, any other data analysis tools compatible with standard data formats (e.g., CSV, Excel) could be used for further analysis and interpretation

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

CSV, ODS formats will be used

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Kristaps Lesinskis (0000-0001-9810-5203)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Dataset on Entrepreneurial Intention and Digital Tool Impact

This dataset originates from the KABADA project and captures survey responses from participants who developed business plans with and without the KABADA digital tool. The same set of questions was administered both before and after the sessions, allowing for a comparative analysis of participants' entrepreneurial intention and readiness to start a business. The results highlight the significant impact of the KABADA tool in fostering entrepreneurial readiness and intention.

Purpose:

The dataset will serve as a training data source for developing, refining, and testing statistical analysis methods to validate hypotheses related to the impact of digital tools, such as KABADA, on fostering entrepreneurial intention (EI). It will enable the research team to explore and confirm the hypothesis and methods that the use of such tools significantly enhances participants' readiness to start a business.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of this dataset is to analyze the impact of digital tools, specifically the KABADA platform, on fostering entrepreneurial intention (EI) and readiness to start a business. The dataset originates from a controlled study where participants developed business plans with and without the KABADA tool.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- ODS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

GitHub

id: <https://github.com/KABADATeam>, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be useful for researchers, educational institutions, policymakers, and development finance organizations interested in understanding the impact of digital tools on entrepreneurial intention and readiness to start a business. It can also aid in the design of better entrepreneurship education programs, focusing on gender differences and the role of AI in enhancing entrepreneurial skills.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

Entrepreneurial Intention, Entrepreneurship Education, Business Plan Development

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

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Yes

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